

Bi Phenom

Multifunctional Biophenols for Safe and Recyclable Materials

Call topic: **HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-02**

Grant Agreement n° **101135107**

D5.1 - Safe and Sustainable by Design methodological framework

Lead Author: Panagiotis Isigonis – LIST

with contributions from: Marjorie Morales, Nirvana
Marting – LIST

Barry Hardy, Ghada Tagorti,
Indrè Piragytè-Langa Oliva – EwC

Reviewed by Marc Borrega, VTT

Deliverable nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual delivery date	31/05/2025
Actual delivery	27/05/2025
version	1.0

Contents

Version history	3
Abstract.....	3
Abbreviations.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. SSbD methodology	6
2.1. Guiding principles	7
2.2. Safety assessment.....	9
2.3. Environmental sustainability assessment.....	10
2.4. Economic and social assessment	14
2.5. Integration of the SSbD evaluation results	16
3. Application of SSbD methodology to BioPhenom.....	17
3.1. Overall BioPhenom processes	17
3.2. State of the art – Literature review	18
3.2.1. Thermoplastic composites.....	18
3.2.2. Carbon fibre thermoset composites.....	19
3.2.3. Exterior wood products.....	20
3.3. SSbD assessment - System boundaries for BioPhenom processes.....	22
3.4. Design alternatives of BioPhenom to be investigated.....	28
3.5. Data requirements.....	28
4. Discussion.....	29
5. References.....	30
Appendices.....	35

Version history

Version	Date	Editors	Description
0.1	06/03/2025	Panagiotis Isigonis	Draft structure and content analysis
0.2	25/04/2025	Marjorie Morales	Updated structure & content
0.3	16/05/2025	Panagiotis Isigonis, Marjorie Morales, Ghada Tagorti	Updated version for internal revision
1.0	26/05/2025	LIST and EwC co-authors	Final version

Abstract

The BioPhenom project intends to apply the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework developed by the European Commission (EC) to support the development of bio-based solutions (e.g., intumescent flame retardants, resins, carbon fibres) in wood, thermosets, and thermoplastics for various application sectors (e.g., building, construction, transportation, automotive, aerospace and electronics.). The application of the SSbD framework intends to ensure the safety and sustainability of the BioPhenom products from the very early stages of innovation and along their life cycle. This deliverable describes how the SSbD framework will be applied within the BioPhenom project, including the methodological background of the different steps and how they will be applied to each BioPhenom product and the relevant sectoral application.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Abbreviations

ACQ: alkaline copper quaternary	MCDA: Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
bio-IFR: bio-based intumescent flame retardant	MCI: Material Circularity Indicator
BPA: bisphenol A	OPFR: organophosphate flame retardants
CCA: chromated copper arsenate	PAN: polyacrylonitrile
ChF: characterisation factor	PEF: Production Environmental Footprint
CF: carbon fibre	PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	PFBS: perfluorobutane sulfonate
DGEBA: diglycidyl ether bisphenol A	PFOA: perfluorooctanoic acid
DNEL: Derived No-Effect Levels	PFHxA: perfluorohexanoic acid
DOPO: 9,10-dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide	PLA: polylactic acid
EC: European Commission	PNEC: Predicted No-Effect Concentrations
EF: environmental footprint	PROC: Process Category
ERC: Environmental Release Category	PS: polystyrene
FR: flame retardant	PU: polyurethane
FU: functional unit	R&I: Research and Innovation
JRC: Joint Research Centre	RCR: Risk Characterisation Ratio
LCA: Life Cycle Assessment	SDS: Safety Data Sheets
LCC: Life Cycle Costing	S-LCA: Social Life Cycle Assessment
LCI: Life Cycle Inventory	SSbD: Safe and Sustainable by Design
LCIA: Life Cycle Impact Assessment	SVHC: Substances of Very High Concern
	TRL: technology readiness level
	VRE: value-based resource efficiency

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting – Innovate UK Council [1005409].

1. Introduction

The European Green Deal, as adopted in October 2020 by the European Commission (EC), incorporates the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) to support the “zero pollution” and other ambitions of the EC [1]. The CSS aims at phasing out the most harmful substances and materials, and the promotion of the production and use of safer and more sustainable alternatives. While increasing safety is the first concern of the CSS, other sustainability aspects are also considered to contribute to other pillars of the European Green Deal, such as the climate neutrality or circular economy. The objective is also to adopt a life cycle approach to understand the impact along the different stages of the materials, from production to use and disposal, and thus avoid regrettable substitution thanks to a comprehensive approach.

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the EC developed a framework to develop “safe and sustainable by design” (SSbD) chemicals and materials and thus support research and innovation (R&I) activities for the development of alternatives to hazardous substances. The framework was published in 2022 [2], following the adoption of the recommendation by the EC [3]. The SSbD framework defines the general approach, provides guidance for the definition of safety and sustainability criteria, and describes the related evaluation procedures. The SSbD framework has undergone its 1st testing period, through the systematic collection of feedback from stakeholders (2023-2024) and a revised version is expected in the second half of 2025.

The BioPhenom project intends to apply the SSbD framework to support the development of the bio-based solutions (e.g., intumescent flame retardants, resins, carbon fibres) and ensure their safety and sustainability. This deliverable describes how the SSbD framework will be applied within the BioPhenom project. An overview of the methodological background is provided in section 0, followed by a detailed description of the settings of the SSbD framework (i.e., definition of system boundaries, scenarios and data requirements) for each BioPhenom sectoral application in section 3.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting – Innovate UK Council [1005409].

2. SSbD methodology

The SSbD framework aims at guiding the design of new materials and verify their compliance with safety and sustainability criteria. The framework has thus two components:

- The **(re)design phase** where design guiding principles can support design choices based on practical actions and technical indicators to monitor the implementation of these actions (e.g., material efficiency guiding principle can be achieved by improving the recovery of unreacted chemicals, which can be measured by the net mass of materials consumed and the recovery rate).
- The **safety and sustainability assessment** phase where these dimensions and related indicators are evaluated to check their alignment with criteria and thus identify if new design alternatives need to be investigated (if trade-offs were observed) or if further development can continue.

This stepwise approach is intended to be applied along the innovation processes, from low technology readiness levels (TRL) to the final market deployment, to be able to identify as soon as possible safety or sustainability issues and thus facilitate the implementation of corrective actions. The SSbD framework is thus a continuous process with several iterations along the various innovation steps.

Besides this, the EC adopted a hierarchical approach between the dimensions, with safety aspects considered first (due to the main objective of the CSS), followed by environmental, social, and economic aspects. The methods to support socio-economic sustainability are less mature, which explains why the EC considers their evaluation as an optional step for now.

The following sub-sections detail the methodologies used in BioPhenom, following the SSbD framework, starting with the guiding design principles (section 2.1). Then, the five steps for the safety and sustainability assessment are described:

- **Step 1** – Hazard assessment of the chemical/material
- **Step 2** – Human health and safety aspects in the chemical/material production and processing phase
- **Step 3** – Human health and environmental aspects in the final application phase
- **Step 4** – Environmental sustainability assessment (section 2.3)
- **Step 5** – Socio-economic assessment (section 2.4)

For convenience, the steps 1, 2 and 3 are grouped into one single sub-section dealing with safety evaluation (section 0). The last sub-section (0) provides a short introduction to the integration of the evaluation results of the SSbD methodology produced during the 5 steps of the framework and how the project consortium aims at integrating the results of the case studies for extracting consolidated results.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

2.1. Guiding principles

The SSbD framework intends to support the design of new chemicals or materials, at the molecular level (influencing the intrinsic properties of the new substances), process level (investigating the production operating conditions), or at product level (in which the new chemical/material is integrated). To do so, the EC promotes guiding principles which should contribute to improved safety and sustainability performances (this should always be verified via the subsequent steps of safety and sustainability assessment).

Based on previous scientific initiatives, such as the green chemistry, green engineering, sustainable chemistry or safe by design principles, a set of eight design principles were defined (Table 1). Depending on the feasibility, these principles can be followed by the material developers. It is important to highlight that a material can be promoted as a “SSbD material” only if it complies with safety and sustainability criteria, evaluated with the following steps, while the eight design principles only have a guidance role to increase the chance to be compliant with the safety and sustainability criteria. This support role is emphasized by the fact that the EC makes it optional to report the adherence to SSbD principles.

For each SSbD principle, a short definition, and examples of actions to implement it and of indicators to monitor it are provided in Table 1. The indicators are related to technical design aspects, which the material developers can easily relate to. Some of them refer to circularity aspects, such as the recycled content and the share of renewable energy for SSbD4, the ability to recycle the material for SSbD7, or the value-based resource efficiency (VRE) and the material circularity indicator (MCI) for SSbD8. In BioPhenom, these circularity indicators will also be calculated for the investigated design alternatives.

Table 1. SSbD guiding principles from the EC [2].

SSbD principle	Definition	Examples of actions	Examples of indicators
SSbD1 Material efficiency	Reducing the use of raw materials and the generation of waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximise reaction yield - Recover unreacted chemicals - Optimise solvent for purpose 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Net mass of materials consumed (kg/kg) - Reaction yield - Total amount of waste (kg/kg)
SSbD2 Minimise the use of hazardous chemicals/materials	Preserve functionality while reducing or avoid using hazardous materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eliminate hazardous materials - Analysis of using hazardous materials in close loops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classification of raw materials as SVHC - Biodegradability of manufactured chemical/material (yes/no)

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

SSbD3 Design for energy efficiency	Minimise the overall energy used to produce/process a chemical/material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximise energy re-use (e.g., heat networks integration) - Fewer production steps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy consumption (kWh/kg or MJ/kg) - Boiling temperature (°C) - Energy efficiency (%)
SSbD4 Use renewable sources	Closing the loops or using renewable or secondary material and energy sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select renewable or secondary materials that do not create land competition and/or processes - Use renewable energy sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of renewable feedstock (%) - Share of renewable energy (%) - Recycled content (%)
SSbD5 Prevent and avoid hazardous emissions	Apply technologies to minimise or avoid hazardous emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select materials and/or processes that minimise the generation of hazardous waste - Emissions (e.g., VOCs, metals) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical air mass (%) - Biological oxygen demand (g/kg) - Wastewater to treatment (m³/kg) - Amount of hazardous waste (kg/kg)
SSbD6 Reduce exposure to hazardous substances	Eliminate exposure to chemical hazards (combine SSbD2 and SSbD5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid as much as possible SVHC - Consider value chain regulations - Eliminate hazardous substances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classification of raw materials as SVHC - Biodegradability of manufactured chemical/material (yes/no)
SSbD7 Design for end-of-life	Design chemicals/materials so that waste products do not pose any risk and do not hinder reuse, sorting and recycling/upcycling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid chemicals that hamper the recycling processes - Select materials that are more durable, easy to separate or truly biodegradable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recyclable? (yes/no) - Durability (years) - Disassembly/reparability design (yes/no)
SSbD8 Consider the whole life cycle	Apply the other design principles through the entire life cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using reusable packaging along the supply chain - Energy-efficient logistics - Responsible sourcing principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value-based resource efficiency indicator (VRE) - Material circularity indicator (MCI) - Durability (years)

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

2.2. Safety assessment

The safety assessment consists of three steps, following the approach outlined in the JRC report [4]:

Step 1 involves evaluating the hazard classification of a chemical based on hazard codes. A scoring system is applied according to defined criteria: if a chemical meets specific classification thresholds for a given endpoint, a corresponding score is assigned. If data are lacking for an endpoint, a justification must be provided. The relevant endpoints are listed in the JRC report (Figure 1). A score of 0 in this step is considered a cut-off criterion for progressing with the SSbD assessment (Figure 2).

Step 2 and **Step 3** focus on human health and environmental aspects. Relevant Process Categories (PROC)s and Environmental Release Categories (ERC)s should be identified through databases and literature to estimate worker exposure levels. For consumers, the conditions of use should be identified in order to estimate exposure levels accurately. These values are then used to calculate the Risk Characterisation Ratio (RCR). Based on the total RCR, a scoring system is applied for both Step 2 and Step 3.

Group definition	Human health hazards	Environmental hazards	Physical hazards
Includes the <u>most harmful substances</u> (according to CSS (EC, 2020a)), including the <u>substances of very high concern</u> (SVHC) according to REACH Art. 57(a-f) ^{20,21} (EU, 2006). These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H1</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carcinogenicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (human health) • Respiratory sensitisation Cat. 1 • Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 1, including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic / very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB) • Persistent, mobile and toxic / very persistent and mobile (PMT/vPvM) • Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (environment) 	
Includes <u>substances of concern</u> , as described in CSS (EC, 2020a), defined in the Article 2(28) of SPI proposal (EC, 2022b) ²² and that are not already included in Criterion H1. These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H2</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin sensitisation Cat. 1 • Carcinogenicity Cat. 2 • Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 2 • Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 2 • Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 2 • Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 1 and 2 • Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (human health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hazardous for the ozone layer • Chronic environmental toxicity (chronic aquatic toxicity) • Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (environment) 	
Includes the <u>other hazard classes</u> not part already in Criteria H1 and H2. These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H3</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute toxicity • Skin corrosion • Skin irritation • Serious eye damage/eye irritation • Aspiration hazard (Cat. 1) • Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute environmental toxicity (acute aquatic toxicity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explosives • Flammable gases, liquids and solids • Aerosols • Oxidising gases, liquids, solids • Gases under pressure • Self-reactive • Pyrophoric liquids, solid • Self-heating • In contact with water emits flammable gas • Organic peroxides • Corrosivity • Desensitised explosives

Figure 1. Overview of the group classification and hazard categories (from [2]).

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Figure 2. Scoring system for Step 1 of SSbD framework [4].

2.3. Environmental sustainability assessment

For the assessment of environmental sustainability, the standardized Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, as specified in ISO 14040/44, is recommended by the EC. This comprehensive approach is designed to evaluate all potential environmental impacts of a product or process across its entire life cycle, allowing for the identification of any potential burden transfer between stages or impact types. The LCA process, as outlined by ISO 14040/44, involves the following four key iterative steps, where the practitioner can go back to a previous stage to re-define some assumptions, improve data collection or test new scenarios.

- o **Goal and Scope Definition:** this step involves defining the purpose of the study (i.e., objective), the scope, and the boundaries of the system being assessed. It clarifies what product or process is being analysed (i.e., the functional unit), the level of detail required, the intended application of the results, and other methodological choices.
- o **Inventory Analysis (LCI, Life Cycle Inventory):** In this phase, data is collected on all inputs (such as energy, materials, and resources) and outputs (like emissions, waste, and products)

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER, State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

associated with each stage of the product's life cycle. This data is used to build a life cycle inventory. All the input and output flows of the studied processes are defined as foreground data and complemented with generic data to reflect the upstream and downstream processes, also called background data.

- o **Impact Assessment (LCIA, Life Cycle Impact Assessment):** The data collected in the inventory analysis (e.g., emissions of pollutants and used natural resources) is evaluated to assess its potential environmental impacts. This step involves categorizing the data into impact categories (e.g., global warming potential, ozone depletion, acidification) and characterized according to their effect and the unit of reference of each impact category (conversion of physical unit from LCI, e.g., mass, to impact unit, e.g., kg CO₂ eq., via characterization factors (ChFs), e.g., in kg CO₂ eq./kg reflecting the radiative forcing of the greenhouse gas over 100 years compared to the one of CO₂).
- o **Results interpretation:** The final step involves analysing the results, depending on the goal of the study and on the quality of the evaluation, e.g., including contribution, sensitivity or uncertainty analysis, to draw relevant conclusions. This step identifies significant issues, and provides recommendations based on the findings. It ensures that the results are consistent with the goal and scope defined in the first step, and it helps guide decision-making for improving environmental performance.

Within the BioPhenom project, the definition of the goal and scope will be determined for each case study, considering the system boundaries, evaluated scenarios, and functional unit (see **section 3**). About the other aspects, the common objective is to support the design of new materials by comparing the environmental impacts of different design alternatives against reference values. The targeted audience is primarily the BioPhenom partners involved in the development of new materials and their processing steps. The evaluation results may, however, be communicated externally to support R&I activities for the development of similar SSbD materials, as well as to policymakers.

LCI data will be collected from project partners (see **section 3.3** for data collection template) and will be complemented with ecoinvent data (version 3.9.1 or later if available) for background processes. Following the recommendations from the SSbD framework, besides ISO 14040/44 standards, the LCIA will be performed according to the Production Environmental Footprint (PEF) method [5], which defines additional rules to increase the replicability and comparability of LCA results. The Environmental Footprint (EF) method [6] includes a total of 16 impact categories (Table 2), related to toxicity (freshwater ecotoxicity and human toxicity, carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects), climate change, pollution (ozone depletion, particulate matter, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation, acidification, eutrophication) and resources use (land, water, mineral and metals, and energy carriers).

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Table 2. Description of EF impact categories for environmental sustainability evaluation [6].

LCA Assessment level	Impact category	Description	Unit
Toxicity (Criteria E1)	Human toxicity, cancer	Increased cancer diseases in human population	CTUh ¹
	Human toxicity, non-cancer	Increased non-cancer cases in human population	CTUh ¹
	Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Potentially affected fraction of aquatic species	CTUe ²
Climate change (Criteria E2)	Climate change	Radiative forcing of GHGs over 100 years	kg CO ₂ eq
Pollution (Criteria E3)	Ozone depletion	Destructive effects on the stratospheric ozone layer over 100 years	kg CFC-11 eq
	Particulate matter	Disease incidence due to particulate matter emissions	disease incidences
	Ionizing radiation	Human exposure to radioactive material	kBq U235 eq
	Photochemical ozone formation	Tropospheric ozone concentration increases due to VOCs oxidation	kg NMVOC eq
	Acidification	Critical load exceedance in terrestrial ecosystems due to acidifying substances deposition	molc H ⁺ eq
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	Critical load exceedance in terrestrial ecosystems due to eutrophying substances deposition	mol N eq
	Eutrophication, freshwater	Increase of phosphorous concentration in water	kg P eq
	Eutrophication, marine	Increase of nitrogen concentration in water	kg N eq
Resources (Criteria E4)	Land use	Index of soil quality	Dimensionless ³
	Water use	Deprivation-weighted water consumption	m ³ water eq. of deprived water
	Resource use, minerals and metals	Mineral and metals resource depletion based on use-to-availability ratio	kg Sb eq
	Resource use, energy carriers	Fossil resources depletion based on lower heating values	MJ

¹Comparative toxic unit for humans; ²Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems; ³Index reflecting land use impacts from four indicators provided by LANCA model.

The characterisation of ecotoxicity and human toxicity impacts for the EF method is based on the consensual USEtox method [7] covering the different steps of the cause-effect chain: fate, exposure, and effect. Currently the EF v3.1 method includes the characterization factors (ChFs) for 3319 organic compounds for human toxicity, non-cancer and 1023 organics for cancer effects. Thus, not all potentially toxic substances are represented. Many hazardous organic pollutants, such as Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and Organophosphate Flame Retardants (OPFRs), pose significant challenges for environmental impact assessment for missing ChFs. To address this, some researchers have developed new ChFs to evaluate the toxicological impacts of related emissions, which are typically expressed in units of comparative toxicity (CTUh/kg emitted for human toxicity and CTUe/kg emitted

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

for ecotoxicity). Several studies have calculated potential ecotoxicological ChFs for a range of substances, including pharmaceutical and personal care products (e.g., acetaminophen, amoxicillin, and lorazepam) [8], textile chemicals, and certain PFAS compounds (e.g., Perfluorooctanoic acid - PFOA, Perfluorohexanoic acid - PFHxA, and Perfluorobutane sulfonate - PFBS), as reported by Holmquist et al. [9] and Roos et al. [10]. Furthermore, Morales et al. [11] have transparently reported new ChFs for 21 OPFRs, bisphenol A (BPA), and 39 PFAS using the USEtox model, detailing the data sources and input parameters used. These updated ChFs provide a valuable resource for future studies assessing the toxicity impacts of these substances. However, limitations remain — notably, the exclusion of terminal degradation products due to insufficient data. Additionally, the long half-lives of some organic pollutants hinder empirical observation of their degradation pathways, necessitating the use of advanced modelling approaches (Morales et al., 2024).

To evaluate the environmental sustainability of a new material/process, criteria should be defined as a reduction of impact category value of X% relative to a reference value. This definition entails the specification of two aspects: the reference value and the minimum percentage of impact reduction.

Conventionally in LCA, the reference value would be defined as the impacts of the material/process replaced by the new one, fulfilling the same function. In the case of BioPhenom, the use of bio-based intumescent flame retardants (bio-IFRs) will contribute to replacing fossil and harmful substances commonly classified as Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) due to toxicity. The reference scenario would depend on each case study: a) for the thermoplastic biocomposites case studies it will be the replacement of **melamine and brominated flame retardants**; b) for the biocarbon fibre (bio-CF) thermosets case studies it will be the replacement of **acrylonitrile** in the synthesis of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and **BPA** in the production of bioepoxy resins; c) for the impregnated wood products case studies it will be the replacement of **boron** compounds.

Regarding the setting of the percentage of impact reduction in the criteria definition, the JRC does not provide much guidance but only an example with 4 levels (see Table 2), ranging from ‘no improvement’ to an ‘improvement above 40%’, where the material is considered to pass the criteria for an improvement higher than 5% [2]. The authors highlight the need to consider the uncertainty of the assessment to define these levels. This aspect will be investigated in the BioPhenom project, where the reliability of the LCA will be considered to define the criteria. A key aspect is to avoid that BioPhenom materials generate significant additional impacts, where the definition of significant will depend on the evaluation uncertainties. Conversely, the materials will be considered better than the reference value if a significant reduction in impacts is achieved. The significance may evolve throughout the project, as the quality of data is expected to improve with more representative measurements from the pilot processes.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

In addition, for the reference value, the JRC recommends adopting a more ambitious approach to reach not only relative sustainability but the so-called “absolute sustainability” where the impacts of the new developed material comply with the “planetary boundaries”. The latter are threshold values for nine environmental aspects, which must not be transgressed to avoid unacceptable environmental change. The definition of the planetary boundaries and their downscaling to a specific process are still under development and no consensual method exist yet, although some works were performed in literature [12]. As a simplified approach, the JRC used a factor of 10 between the current EU production and consumption impacts and the acceptable limits. Further research is needed to consolidate the definition of relevant reference values. In BioPhenom, while the new bio-based solutions for wooden, thermoset, and thermoplastic materials will be firstly used, more ambitious targets aligned with the planetary boundaries will be explored along the project duration.

2.4. Economic and social assessment

Economic sustainability under the SSbD framework considers not only the direct costs associated with a compound but also its broader life cycle from raw material sourcing to the point at which the final product leaves the factory. This includes assessing the availability of compounds, which is a critical factor in ensuring supply chain resilience and production continuity.

In addition to the direct production costs such as raw materials, economic sustainability also accounts for indirect costs. These may include machinery investment, workforce salaries, consumables, and even the costs associated with emissions. These considerations provide a more comprehensive understanding of the true financial footprint of a product. This holistic approach to economic evaluation falls under the broader concept of Life Cycle Costing (LCC).

The LCC in this pilot phase will be estimated based on a combination of laboratory-scale data and data extracted from reputable scientific databases and peer-reviewed articles. This approach ensures a foundational understanding of cost dynamics using the best available evidence at this early stage. It is worth noting that one of the key challenges in conducting an accurate economic assessment lies in the variability of the biophenols mixture quality. The quality of this mixture plays a significant role in determining the overall cost, as different quality grades can command substantially different price points in the market.

The first-tier assessment is based on estimations. As this is a pilot project, the figures derived may not fully reflect the realities of full-scale industrial production. Once the transition to large-scale manufacturing begins, several variables could significantly influence the final LCC.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

The social dimension of sustainability will be assessed via a **Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of the type of Reference Scale Assessment** [13]. This type of study assesses social risks instead of social impacts. Social risks associated with processes are determined by social and socio-economic conditions given in countries or country-sectors involved, the amount of input required in a process and the number of worker-hours required to produce an input.

Social hotspots considering the foreground and background systems will be identified. Social hotspots are defined as processes taking place at specific locations (typically countries) where a social aspect is of high risk for the stakeholders. S-LCA will be conducted using the existing databases PSILCA [14] and/or Soca [15]. Being based on Input-Output tables, PSILCA provides results at sectoral level. Soca is the result of mapping worker-hours contained in PSILCA on ecoinvent processes, considering input prices to convert worker-hours per monetary unit to worker-hours per process reference flow (kg, item, MJ, etc). In consequence, inventories created to perform the environmental LCA using the ecoinvent database are useful (with no need of further data processing) to conduct the S-LCA with the Soca database.

Worker-hours required for production processes for the foreground system will be ideally collected from project partners, while background data for worker-hours is available in databases. Considering that the technologies in the BioPhenom project are in early stages, worker hours for the foreground system data might be difficult to estimate. Furthermore, lab scale processes tend to require a high number of worker-hours in comparison to industrial scale processes. In this sense, a sensitivity analysis considering different scales will be performed. Worker-hours from similar industries contained in databases can be used as proxies for the industrial scale.

PSILCA and Soca databases are structured in a way that various stakeholders are considered, these are local community, society, workers and value chain actors. Each stakeholder contains different indicators. For instance, the stakeholder worker presents indicators concerning child and forced labour, fair salary, trade unionism, rate of accidents at the workplace, among others. The risk assessment will consider all indicators contained in the databases, and the results will show processes taking place at specific locations where high risks are likely to occur.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

2.5. Integration of the SSbD evaluation results

The SSbD framework defines one cut-off criterion for step 1 regarding the hazard properties of the materials/chemicals, while a score is attributed to the other aspects in steps 2, 3, 4 and 5 depending on the defined criteria. A chemical/material can be considered SSbD if the safety and environmental sustainability are met (socio-economic sustainability is not yet mandatory). When a chemical/material fails a criterion, the latter could be investigated to find solutions for improvement.

In BioPhenom, quantitative evaluation of various design alternatives will be performed for the safety, environmental and economic sustainability criteria, while qualitative results on the overall BioPhenom concept will be obtained from the social acceptance survey (see section 2.4). The social dimension will thus not be included to support the design choices but could be included as additional qualitative results to understand the acceptance level and barriers of the final BioPhenom materials.

In order to rank different design alternatives based on safety, environmental and economic sustainability assessment results, multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) can be applied to aggregate all the results and support decisions. Several MCDA techniques exist and can provide different types of outcomes. The JRC [2] highlights several requisites and their implications to perform such an assessment. A first key point is the consideration of data quality, which can vary depending on new or existing chemicals/materials and affect the results. Then, both ratings (e.g., poor, good, very good) or numerical values can be used (depending on the defined SSbD criteria). As highlighted previously, the EC aspires to move from a relative evaluation to an absolute one where each chemical or material is evaluated based on its own merits and not compared to other chemicals or materials. Finally, while the hierarchical approach should be respected (safety first), the JRC does not allow for trade-offs between safety and environmental performance, i.e., compensation effects should be minimized. To comply with these requirements, aggregation methods based on IF-THEN rules (e.g., Decision Expert DEX, Dominance based Rouch Set Approach DRSA) or on concordance-discordance voting analysis (e.g., ELECTRE TRI, which proves a good rating if positive results are obtained on sufficient aspects without strong opposition from any of the evaluated aspects) are recommended.

In BioPhenom, the targeted TRL at the end of the project for the new developed materials is TRL 5. Intermediate and final SSbD evaluation along the project will still contain significant uncertainties, and more accurate data could be obtained at higher TRL scales. Due to the expected low to medium data quality for the SSbD evaluation, the exclusion of design alternatives because they do not bring significant safety or sustainability benefits is not intended. However, options which are expected to generate significant trade-offs (after considering the range of possible data values) could be excluded. While the results on each aspect of safety, environmental and economic sustainability will be analysed

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting -
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

to understand the advantages and disadvantages of BioPhenom materials and processes, MCDA techniques will be tested to facilitate the ranking of design alternatives, following the recommendations of the EC. The results will be interpreted based on the data quality, recognising that the SSbD rating will need to be updated during the next phases of the materials development (up to TRL 9).

3. Application of SSbD methodology to BioPhenom

This section details the settings for the safety, environmental sustainability, and socio-economic assessment of the biophenol extraction processes through pyrolysis and liquid extraction, and further use of the extracted biophenols in the BioPhenom material case studies (thermoplastic biocomposites, thermoset biocomposites (bio-CFs and bioepoxy resins), and bio-impregnated wood) which will be then scoped and applied in various applications to be selected from an initial pool of options (i.e., building & construction, automotive, transportation, aerospace, and electronics).

3.1. Overall BioPhenom processes

The project aims to develop isolating methods for biophenols from biomass side streams by liquid extraction and fast pyrolysis. The isolated biophenols are then functionalized into bio-IFRs by addition of nitrogen and exploited as multifunctional components to replace SVHC used in the formulation of:

- Thermoplastic composites
- Carbon fibre thermoset composites
- Impregnated wood products

Bio-IFRs are used as precursors in the production of bio-CFs and bio-based epoxy resins, and as additives in thermoplastic biocomposites. Additionally, they serve as impregnation agents that impart biocidal and flame retardant properties, enhancing the biological durability and fire resistance of solid wood.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

3.2. State of the art – Literature review

3.2.1. Thermoplastic composites

Thermoplastic composites used in insulation and load-bearing applications typically contain materials like polyurethane (PU) or polystyrene (PS) [16], [17]. These are made from petrochemical-based substances — for example, isocyanates and styrene — that are known to be toxic. Isocyanates are a possible carcinogen, highly irritant, and may cause severe respiratory effects among other health hazards [16], while styrene is associated with reproductive and pre-natal development toxicity [17].

Because PU and PS are highly flammable, manufacturers usually add flame retardants (FRs) to meet fire safety standards. One common group of FRs includes melamine-based compounds, which are classified as SVHC due to their potential health and environmental risks [18]. Reports in the scientific literature provide information on combinations of conventional FRs with bio-based components, which may be considered safer but continue to still have significant drawbacks [19]:

- Low flame-retardant performance
- High costs and complicated manufacturing processes, often involving hazardous chemicals
- A tendency for the flame retardants to leach out or migrate over time, reducing effectiveness and possibly causing environmental contamination of aquatic ecosystems.

However, incorporation of bio-IFRs in thermoplastics would replace melamine-based compounds. Traditional thermoplastic materials are harmful to both the environment and human health, and recycling them is difficult and expensive. Researchers are looking into using PLA-based thermoplastic composites instead. PLA (polylactic acid) is a biodegradable plastic made from renewable resources like corn starch or sugarcane. It is mechanically recyclable, meaning it can be reprocessed into new materials without using harsh chemicals. When combined with biochar (a carbon-rich material made from biomass), these PLA-based biocomposites can [20]:

- Improve mechanical strength (they're stronger and more durable),
- Enhance FR performance (they're more resistant to fire),
- Still be more eco-friendly compared to traditional plastics.

BioPhenom aims to advance beyond current technologies by developing PLA-biochar thermoplastic composites enhanced with bio-IFRs to significantly improve fire resistance. These next-generation composites will be bio-based, fire resistant, free from SVHC, and recyclable through melting and reformulation into new composite products.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

In addition to conventional melt-processing methods, the BioPhenom project will also test a new method — using electro-spraying or electro-spinning to better mix components on PLA sheets before moulding — to enhance material quality.

There are several LCAs of PLA or comparing different thermoplastics with PLA in terms of environmental aspects, energy demand, and greenhouse gases emissions [21]. These LCAs comparing PLA thermoplastics with other plastics show that, while bio-based polymers like PLA absorb more CO₂ during production than fossil-based ones, their manufacturing still relies heavily on fossil fuels. The process of converting bio-sources into lactic acid and then into PLA is energy-intensive and produces significant CO₂—over 50% of PLA’s total emissions (about 2.8 kg CO₂ per kg of PLA) come from this conversion step. Improving this process could significantly reduce PLA’s carbon footprint, making it a more sustainable material. According to the available data, more than 50% (2.8 kg CO₂/kg PLA) of the released CO₂ in the PLA life cycle belongs to its conversion. By optimizing the conversion process of PLA, there will be a high potential to make PLA a low-carbon material.

3.2.2. Carbon fibre thermoset composites

Most of the carbon fibres (CFs) produced globally are derived from acrylonitrile, a monomer that is known to be carcinogenic, neurotoxic, a skin irritant, and hazardous to aquatic organisms [22]. After polymerization into polyacrylonitrile (PAN), the material must be oxidised, carbonised, and graphitised — a process during which carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen cyanide are released.

Replacing the petroleum-derived PAN precursor of CFs with green biopolymers can potentially enhance the sustainability of the carbon fibre industry, but how this replacement can mitigate carbon emissions is still elusive. The study developed by Wang et al. [23] performed a LCA on the alternative of a plant-derived lignin biopolymer from biorefining waste for the replacement of PAN in CF production. The LCA study revealed that CFs made from PAN could induce carbon emissions of 23.3 kg CO₂-eq per kg of CF, while 50% replacement of PAN with lignin led to carbon emissions of 19.5 kg CO₂-eq per kg of CF, representing a 16.3% reduction in carbon emissions. However, lignin must first be fractionated and/or blended with synthetic polymers before it can be used. Analysis of the main contributions to carbon emissions from processing demonstrated that among the different production factors, consumed electricity generated the highest carbon emissions, followed by the precursor PAN.

In the BioPhenom project, the state-of-the-art will be surpassed by producing bio-CFs from non-toxic polymeric bio-IFRs, with low-molecular-weight biophenols being used as processing aids during carbonisation. Through this approach, bio-IFRs will be used to replace acrylonitrile in the synthesis of

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

PAN. The bio-CFs will be fabricated using a novel nanofibre-forming process [24], through which post-processing will allow for improved molecular alignment, enhancing mechanical properties.

BioPhenom will advance the state-of-the-art by using clean wet-filament winding to impregnate bio-CFs with a bio-based, flame-retardant epoxy resin, enhancing fire resistance. Using bio-IFRs in resin production reduces reliance on BPA, which is included on ECHA's SVHC list due to its human and environmental health hazards [25]. BPA also leaches out of epoxy resins, further endangering consumers.

Conventional thermoset composites rely on DGEBA (diglycidyl ether bisphenol A) epoxy resin systems, which include BPA, a harmful substance classified as an SVHC [26]. These resins also use epichlorohydrin and hardeners, and often include FRs such as: DOPO (9,10-dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide) made from a carcinogenic petrochemical (2-phenyl phenol) and melamine, another SVHC. However, all these chemicals complicate recycling. Once cured, thermoset resins cannot be reshaped, making resin recovery impossible. While Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs) offer recyclable alternatives, they remain in early research [27]. Bio-based epoxies are being developed using plant-derived epichlorohydrin and natural BPA substitutes like lignin and vanillin [28].

BioPhenom will go beyond the state-of-the-art also by:

- Developing a fully bio-based, flame-retardant epoxy system using bio-IFRs (bio-based flame retardants) to replace BPA.
- Using biochar to further boost fire resistance.
- Introducing a special "dynamic" hardener with cleavable bonds, allowing the composite to be easily repaired and recycled in green solvents, e.g., γ -valerolactone.

3.2.3. Exterior wood products

Wood products intended for exterior applications are often treated with preservatives (biocides) and/or impregnated with FRs to meet biological durability and fire safety standards. Common preservatives such as propiconazole have been listed by ECHA as candidates for substitution [29], while copper-based preservatives (e.g., ACQ, MCQ, Cu-azole) are used widely, though they render the treated wood unrecyclable for other wood applications.

FRs such as melamine and brominated compounds are classified as SVHC [30], [31] and are either already restricted or expected to be restricted. Phosphorus-based FRs like polyphosphates are required in high concentrations and are susceptible to leaching.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Boron compounds, currently the only dual-function (FR and preservative) impregnants, continue to be used due to a lack of safer alternatives, despite being classified as SVHC and prone to leaching in outdoor conditions [32]. In recent years, LCA has been widely used by the wood preservation industry to assess the environmental impact of packaging and wood-based products. Studies have covered various treatments, including borate, pentachlorophenol, ACQ (alkaline copper quaternary), CCA (chromated copper arsenate), and creosote for applications such as lumber, utility poles, guardrails, and railroad ties [33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38].

In addition, fast pyrolysis bio-oils have been investigated as preservative treatments [39], while biophenols such as tannins and lignin have been identified as promising FRs when modified with nitrogen groups [40]. A LCA was conducted on tannin-boron wood preservatives and various industrially treated timbers by Hu et al. [41], where chromium-based inorganic salts, and ACQ preservatives, were used for comparison. The results indicated that the environmental impact of tannin-boron systems is significantly influenced by the factors associated with tannin extraction. However, due to the variability in tannin processing methods and findings across studies, further investigation is needed to clarify its impact at an industrial scale.

Fossil-based and hazardous substances currently used as wood preservatives and FRs will be replaced in BioPhenom, with a focus on eliminating boron compounds, the only dual-function wood treatment still in use, despite their SVHC classification and known toxic effects on humans and ecosystems [42]. In BioPhenom, wood will be impregnated with bio-IFRs to simultaneously improve biological durability and fire resistance. These bio-IFRs, which combine the char-forming properties of biophenols with nitrogen groups that induce intumescence, will be used to replace FRs classified as SVHCs. Durability will be enhanced through the natural antifungal and anti-termite properties of biophenols, rather than toxic biocides or heavy metals, which hinder recyclability. Additionally, a novel protective topcoat will be developed to be compatible with the impregnated wood, reducing leaching and extending service life. The resulting wood will be SVHC-free and recyclable into wood-based panels like particleboard, while retaining its biocidal and flame-retardant properties.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

3.3. SSbD assessment - System boundaries for BioPhenom processes

Based on the EC recommendation for SSbD, a cradle to grave LCA will be performed for the manufacturing of the new BioPhenom materials (for wood, thermosets, and thermoplastics), including:

- Biomass (side streams) production and collection.
- Formulation of the new materials, including isolation and functionalization of biophenols, formulation of wood products, carbon fibres, epoxy resin, and thermoplastic composites.
- Materials application and manufacturing process for the final products (bio-impregnated wood production, bio-CF thermoset biocomposites production, and biothermoplastics production).
- Transport and use of the final products.
- Disposal and recycling of the final products.

The safety assessment will first focus on the hazard properties of the used materials (step 1 - Figure 3), while the safety risks will be evaluated depending on the emissions during the production and processing steps (step 2), as well as during the use phase (step 3).

Two main processing routes have been identified and are evaluated in the BioPhenom project for the isolation of biophenols. These routes are:

- Fast pyrolysis (Figure 4)
- Liquid extraction (Figure 5)

To implement the SSbD workflow, a structured approach was developed to address Steps 1–3 of the safety assessment process. The primary objective was to collect data from available open-source databases and to retrieve and extract additional information from Safety Data Sheets (SDS) using an SDS parser [43]. Data is extracted based on the most up-to-date version of each source. In cases of conflicting values, value selection is given to data from open databases due to their standardized and traceable nature. In addition, to facilitate access to regulatory toxicology data, a dedicated REACH Database and associated notebooks have been developed [44], [45], [46], [47]. This notebook supports AI-assisted models and workflows, enabling efficient data retrieval and integration. Within Task 5.1, a workflow documentation tool named NAMASTOX [48] has been also incorporated to ensure reproducibility. This tool will not only help illustrate each step in the assessment process but also support data visualization and automated generation of comprehensive reports to enhance decision-making and communication.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Figure 3. Overview of the safety assessment (Step 1) workflow for implementation within the SSbD framework

Figure 4. System boundaries for the SSbD evaluation of the Fast Pyrolysis route.

Figure 5. System boundaries for the SSbD evaluation of the Liquid extraction route.

A standardized physico-chemical properties template (Figure 6) has been prepared and circulated to facilitate the collection of relevant physico-chemical property data associated with the compounds of interest (Appendix A). This template is designed to ensure consistency and completeness in retrieving the necessary information. For physical and chemical properties not readily available in the databases or not expected to be generated experimentally by project partners, predictions will be performed using OPERA. However, OPERA does not reliably handle inorganics, metals, or polymers and is restricted to predictions for individual compounds. As such, the development or integration of an additional modelling approach will be necessary to estimate physicochemical properties for mixtures, leveraging OPERA outputs alongside supplementary data sources. All relevant information, whether measured or predicted, will be stored in dedicated databases. In the absence of experimental data, literature reviews will be conducted to identify studies that provide justification for hazard classification for specific endpoints. These endpoints are aligned with the criteria outlined by the JRC for SSbD. If a compound meets the criteria for classification based on at least one endpoint, it will be flagged accordingly. When no suitable *in vitro* data or literature justification is found, the process will proceed to *in silico* methods to identify predicted positive or negative outcomes, taking into account the reliability of the prediction domain. All gathered data will then be integrated to generate a preliminary score, corresponding to Step 1 of the workflow.

PhysChem Properties				
Term	Value	Unit	Date	Source
Molecular weight	12.07	g/mol	01.03.2025	PubChem
Material inputs				
Molecular weight				
Melting point				
Vapour pressure				
Partition coefficient				
Water solubility				
Henry's law constant				
Flash point				

Additional Data				
Term	Description	Date	Source	
Autoflammability/Self-ignition temperature	Autoflammable	01.03.2025	ECHA	
Material inputs				
Autoflammability/Self-ignition temperature				
Flammability				
Explosiveness				
Oxidising properties				
PBT assessment				
STP treatment of the waste				

Figure 6. Screenshot of the template used to collect data for Steps 1–3 under the SSbD framework.

High-quality data are essential for adequately covering the hazards associated with the compounds. However, the physico-chemical properties of mixtures are often unavailable, which presents a significant gap. To address this, it is crucial to integrate both computational predictions and experimental results. Under this approach, the importance of sharing as much relevant data as possible is emphasized. To support this effort, a comprehensive template covering Steps 1, 2, and 3 has been circulated to collect safety and hazard-related data from partners. This template is used to retrieve information such as the hazard codes of compounds, process categories to better understand the manufacturing process, and details about the final product and its intended use to assess potential consumer exposure. Additional variables have also been included, particularly toxicity-related data

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate
UK

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting -
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

such as Derived No-Effect Levels (DNEL) and Predicted No-Effect Concentrations (PNEC), to support a more thorough safety assessment.

A first-tier approach has been applied to a selected case study discussed during the consortium meeting in San Sebastian, November 2024. In the context of phenol and eugenol, the objective was to:

- Enhance awareness and familiarity with the SSbD framework,
- Identify data gaps and key challenges associated with biophenols, and
- Highlight the importance of proper characterization of mixtures when assessing biophenols.

The case of phenol and eugenol was used as the first example to study the SSbD framework, specifically to explore how phenol can be substituted with a biophenol. Eugenol, being a naturally occurring phenolic compound found in clove oil, qualifies as a biophenol. This substitution served purely as a case study to demonstrate and explore the application of the SSbD framework.

The other energy and material flows will be included for the LCA and LCC evaluation. The infrastructures impacts will be neglected for the LCA, while the capital and labour costs will be considered for the LCC.

For the formulation of the new BioPhenom materials, the impacts of the raw materials, energy, additives, transport and waste treatment will be considered. Flows or processes that are observed to have a negligible effect on the results or are estimated not to be affected by the new material could be excluded for the system boundaries, e.g., the installation and infrastructure. The cradle-to-grave LCA will be applied for each BioPhenom material, and its cases studies.

Different reference scenarios (benchmarks products) will be used to evaluate the impact of the new BioPhenom materials, depending on the three main final products:

- Impregnated wood product will be benchmarked against commercial wood products that currently rely on fossil-based and hazardous substances, such as traditional wood preservatives and FRs. Special attention will be given to eliminating boron compounds.
- Thermoplastics will be compared to existing commercial thermoplastics that incorporate brominated and melamine-based flame retardants.
- CF thermosets composites will be evaluated against conventional thermoset composites, specifically those made with BPA-based epoxy resins and acrylonitrile-based carbon fibres.

The same functional unit (FU) should be considered in the BioPhenom and reference scenarios for the LCA and LCC studies. Given the varying functionalities and performance requirements of the three final products, the FUs are defined as follows:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

- 1 m³ of a wood demonstrator (e.g., wood boards), impregnated with selected bio-IFRs and coated with the anti-leach topcoat, intended for use in the European building and construction sector.
- 1 m³ of a thermoplastic demonstrator (e.g., thermoplastic sheet), produced using PLA, biochar, and bio-IFRs, to be used in a broad list of potential European markets, e.g., building, construction, transportation, automotive, aerospace and electronics.
- 1 m³ of a thermoset composite demonstrator (e.g., CF thermoset), manufactured with bio-IFRs and bio-based epoxy resin formulations, to be used in many potential European markets, e.g., transportation, automotive, aerospace and electronics.

3.4. Design alternatives of BioPhenom to be investigated

Within the BioPhenom project, different design alternatives of the new materials and processes will be investigated. To support these design choices beyond technical criteria, intermediate SSbD evaluation will be performed on the following aspects:

- Different biomass side streams as source of biophenols: logging residues, tree barks (both from softwood and hardwood), grape stalks, and olive stones.
- Different isolation of biophenols processes: fast pyrolysis and liquid extraction.
- Different operating conditions for water/solvent-based extraction for the selected side streams: hot water, organic solvents (e.g., acetone or ethanol), alkali solvents (e.g., NaOH).
- Different strategies to incorporate nitrogen into biophenols to convert them into bio-IFRs.

3.5. Data requirements

A data collection template was developed to be able to regularly collect the necessary information to support the material development via SSbD. The file contains information on guiding the user to navigate effectively the different parts of the template, including but not limited to sheets on 'System Boundaries', 'Safety Abbreviations and Information' and 'Physico-chemical Information on Substances'. The introductory part is followed by tailored templates for collection of data for Safety and Sustainability assessment. A 'Material Inventory' has been created and will be regularly updated for each WP of the project. The Sustainability assessment data template covers the following sections (Figure 7):

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

- Safety information: CAS number and the safety data sheet link (if available).
- Flow information: name and specifications of the flow (e.g., electricity from the grid, solid waste to incineration).
- Quantity information: amount of the flow with the respective unit, with additional columns to be filled if several design alternatives exist and affect the quantity value.
- Cost and supplier information: unit price, supplier(s) name and respective location.
- Data source information: name of the data provider, date and any additional information regarding the source of data (e.g., measurement, estimation, literature). This information will be used to evaluate the data quality of the evaluation.

Flow information			Safety information		Quantity information				Cost & supplier information			Data source information			
No. stream	Name	Description	CAS number	MSDS?	Unit	Baseline value	Altern. #1	Altern. #2	Altern. #3	Unit price (€)	Supplier(s)	Locati	Partner	Date	Comments (data source, quality...)
Biowaste selection and collection															
Material inputs															
Stream xx	Palmitoyl	Acylating ager xxx-xx-x			kg	[16.95-101.72]	50.86	50.86	67.81	282.8	ThermoScientific	Italy	Name	18.3.2024	Altern. #1 and #2 from measurement, #3 from calculation
Energy inputs															
Products															
Solid/liquid waste															
Emissions of pollutants															
Capital and labour															
Isolation thermal treatment: Pyrolysis															
Material inputs															

Figure 7. Screenshot of the SSbD data collection file for LCA purposes.

4. Discussion

Within the BioPhenom project, safety, sustainability and socio-economic criteria will be used to steer the design of the newly developed BioPhenom materials and processes and enhance their benefits, following the SSbD framework from the EC. Besides the potential application of design principles such as material efficiency or energy efficiency, the safety and sustainability performances of the new materials and the design alternatives will be evaluated with a life cycle perspective following the JRC stepwise approach.

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER, State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

The three safety steps will be performed using publicly available data, but also filling data gaps thanks to experimental testing and the use of computational models. For environmental sustainability (step 4), LCA methodology will be applied following the PEF method, while socio-economic assessment will be performed with the use of the LCC and S-LCA methodologies.

The deliverable describes the methodological assumptions and choices made for the establishment of the basis of the SSbD assessments and how those will be followed up during the project duration. The SSbD framework implementation process will be considered as a continuously evolving process, which will be enriched with any scientific and methodological development created and published during the project duration.

5. References

- [1] EC, 'COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment', 2020. Accessed: Jul. 05, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:667:FIN>
- [2] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials*. LU: Publications Office, 2022. Accessed: Aug. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/404991>
- [3] EC, *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 of 8 December 2022 establishing a European assessment framework for 'safe and sustainable by design' chemicals and materials*. 2022. Accessed: Mar. 31, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2022/2510/oj/eng>
- [4] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: application of the SSbD framework to case studies*. LU: Publications Office, 2023. Accessed: Aug. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/769211>
- [5] EC, *COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations*. 2021. Accessed: Apr. 30, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=intcom:C%282021%299332>
- [6] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., *Supporting information to the characterisation factors of recommended EF Life Cycle Impact Assessment methods: version 2, from ILCD to EF 3.0*. LU: Publications Office, 2018. Accessed: Apr. 30, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/002447>
- [7] P. Fantke *et al.*, 'USEtox[®] 2.0 Documentation (Version 1.00)', 2017, doi: 10.11581/DTU:00000011.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

- [8] S. Ortiz de García, P. A. García-Encina, and R. Irusta-Mata, 'The potential ecotoxicological impact of pharmaceutical and personal care products on humans and freshwater, based on USEtox™ characterization factors. A Spanish case study of toxicity impact scores', *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 609, pp. 429–445, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.07.148.
- [9] H. Holmquist, P. Fantke, I. T. Cousins, M. Owsianiak, I. Liagkouridis, and G. M. Peters, 'An (Eco)Toxicity Life Cycle Impact Assessment Framework for Per- And Polyfluoroalkyl Substances', *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 6224–6234, May 2020, doi: 10.1021/acs.est.9b07774.
- [10] S. Roos, H. Holmquist, C. Jönsson, and R. Arvidsson, 'USEtox characterisation factors for textile chemicals based on a transparent data source selection strategy', *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 890–903, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11367-017-1330-y.
- [11] M. Morales *et al.*, 'Eco-toxicological and climate change effects of sludge thermal treatments: Pathways towards zero pollution and negative emissions', *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 470, p. 134242, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.134242.
- [12] A. Bjørn *et al.*, 'Review of life-cycle based methods for absolute environmental sustainability assessment and their applications', *Environ. Res. Lett.*, vol. 15, no. 8, p. 083001, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/ab89d7.
- [13] ISO, *ISO 14075:2024 Environmental management — Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment*, 2024. Accessed: May 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/61118.html>
- [14] M. Loubert, K. Maister, C. Di Noi, L. Radwan, A. Ciroth, and M. Srocka, 'PSILCA - A Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database', 1.2, Mar. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://nexus.openlca.org/ws/files/25214>
- [15] GreenDelta, 'Soca v.2 add-on – Adding social impact information to ecoinvent', 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://nexus.openlca.org/ws/files/35734>
- [16] D. Rother and U. Schlüter, 'Occupational Exposure to Diisocyanates in the European Union', *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 893–907, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1093/annweh/wxab021.
- [17] ECHA, 'Assessment of regulatory needs list - ECHA'. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/assessment-regulatory-needs>
- [18] ECHA, 'AGREEMENT OF THE MEMBER STATE COMMITTEE ON THE IDENTIFICATION OF Melamine AS A SUBSTANCE OF VERY HIGH CONCERN under Articles 57 and 59 of Regulation (EC) 1907/2006', 2022. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/470b1aed-0ba9-c47f-c2ba-1a078c5c41a8>
- [19] R. A. Mensah *et al.*, 'A review of sustainable and environment-friendly flame retardants used in plastics', *Polymer Testing*, vol. 108, p. 107511, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2022.107511.
- [20] M. Bartoli, R. Arrigo, G. Malucelli, A. Tagliaferro, and D. Duraccio, 'Recent Advances in Biochar Polymer Composites', *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 12, Art. no. 12, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/polym14122506.
- [21] E. Rezvani Ghomi *et al.*, 'The Life Cycle Assessment for Polylactic Acid (PLA) to Make It a Low-Carbon Material', *Polymers*, vol. 13, no. 11, Art. no. 11, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3390/polym13111854.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting –
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

- [22] ECHA, 'Opinion on scientific evaluation of occupational exposure limits for Acrylonitrile', ECHA/RAC/ O-0000001412-86-188/F, 2018. [Online]. Available: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/acrylonitrile_opinion_en.pdf/102477c9-a961-2c96-5c4d-76fcd856ac19
- [23] S. Wang *et al.*, 'Replacing polyacrylonitrile with Kraft lignin for sustainable carbon fiber manufacturing mitigates carbon emissions', *Green Chem.*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 1031–1043, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1039/D4GC04579C.
- [24] S. SIHENG and F. GERARD, 'Electrospinning apparatus and method for forming aligned fibres', WO2020120985A1, Jun. 18, 2020 Accessed: Apr. 30, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2020120985A1/en>
- [25] ECHA, 'MEMBER STATE COMMITTEE SUPPORT DOCUMENT FOR IDENTIFICATION OF 4,4'-ISOPROPYLDENEDIPHENOL (BISPHENOL A) AS A SUBSTANCE OF VERY HIGH CONCERN BECAUSE OF ITS TOXIC FOR REPRODUCTION (ARTICLE 57 C) PROPERTIES', 2016. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/b10d6a00-8e47-9b14-4f61-c779a8dc8450>
- [26] European Commission. Joint Research Centre. Institute for Health and Consumer Protection, *Updated European Union risk assessment report : 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (bisphenol-A) : human health addendum of February 2008*. LU: Publications Office, 2010. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2788/40301>
- [27] C. J. Kloxin, T. F. Scott, B. J. Adzima, and C. N. Bowman, 'Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs): A Unique Paradigm in Cross-Linked Polymers', *Macromolecules*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 2643–2653, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1021/ma902596s.
- [28] S. Nikafshar, J. Wang, K. Dunne, P. Sangthongantoi, and M. Nejad, 'Choosing the Right Lignin to Fully Replace Bisphenol A in Epoxy Resin Formulation', *ChemSusChem*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1184–1195, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1002/cssc.202002729.
- [29] EC, *Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/2596 of 21 November 2023 renewing the approval of propiconazole as an active substance for use in biocidal products of product-type 8 in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council*. 2023. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/2596/oj/eng
- [30] ECHA, 'ECHA adds nine hazardous chemicals to Candidate List'. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/-/echa-adds-nine-hazardous-chemicals-to-candidate-list>
- [31] ECHA, 'ECHA identifies certain brominated flame retardants as candidates for restriction'. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/fi/-/echa-identifies-certain-brominated-flame-retardants-as-candidates-for-restriction>
- [32] ECHA BCP, 'Biocidal Products Committee (BPC) Opinion on a request according to Article 75(1)(g) of Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 on The evaluation of the availability and suitability of alternatives to boric acid and disodium tetraborate pentahydrate ECHA/BPC/271/2020', 2020. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2166576/borates_final_bpc_opinion_en.pdf/e17d20fd-ac75-7b56-eebf-018d4f94070d?t=1609764308912

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].

- [33] C. A. Bolin and S. T. Smith, 'Life cycle assessment of borate-treated lumber with comparison to galvanized steel framing', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 630–639, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2010.12.005.
- [34] C. A. Bolin and S. T. Smith, 'Life cycle assessment of pentachlorophenol-treated wooden utility poles with comparisons to steel and concrete utility poles', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 2475–2486, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2011.01.019.
- [35] C. A. Bolin and S. T. Smith, 'Life cycle assessment of ACQ-treated lumber with comparison to wood plastic composite decking', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 620–629, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2010.12.004.
- [36] C. A. Bolin and S. T. Smith, 'Life Cycle Assessment of CCA-Treated Wood Highway Guard Rail Posts in the US with Comparisons to Galvanized Steel Guard Rail Posts', vol. 2013, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.4236/jtts.2013.31007.
- [37] C. A. Bolin and S. T. Smith, 'Life Cycle Assessment of Creosote-Treated Wooden Railroad Crossties in the US with Comparisons to Concrete and Plastic Composite Railroad Crossties', vol. 2013, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.4236/jtts.2013.32015.
- [38] C. K. Chau, T. M. Leung, and W. Y. Ng, 'A review on Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Energy Assessment and Life Cycle Carbon Emissions Assessment on buildings', *Applied Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 395–413, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.01.023.
- [39] C. Mattos, M. C. C. Veloso, G. A. Romeiro, and E. Folly, 'Biocidal applications trends of bio-oils from pyrolysis: Characterization of several conditions and biomass, a review', *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, vol. 139, pp. 1–12, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jaap.2018.12.029.
- [40] P. Widsten, S. Salo, T. Hakkarainen, T. L. Nguyen, M. Borrega, and O. Fearon, 'Antimicrobial and Flame-Retardant Coatings Prepared from Nano- and Microparticles of Unmodified and Nitrogen-Modified Polyphenols', *Polymers*, vol. 15, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/polym15040992.
- [41] J. Hu, C. Skinner, G. Ormondroyd, and M.-F. Thevenon, 'Life cycle assessment of a novel tannin-boron association for wood protection', *Sci Total Environ*, vol. 858, no. Pt 1, p. 159739, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159739.
- [42] Risk & Policy Analysts Limited, 'Assessment of the Risk to Consumers from Borates and the Impact of Potential Restrictions on their Marketing and Use', J612/Borates, 2008. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/2427/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/native&ved=2ahUKEwiR8-PV4KeNAXWFK_sDHSLIFFIQFnoECBwQAQ&usg=AOvVaw2pzKVfHBGhSnd__Kz3zzze
- [43] Edelweiss Connect, 'SDS Toolbox'. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sds-toolbox.edelweissconnect.com/>
- [44] SaferWorldbyDesign, 'Chemical similarity search on RDT studies from REACH database / SaferWorldbyDesign', Observable. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://observablehq.com/@saferworldbydesign/chemical-similarity-search-on-rdt-studies-from-rea>
- [45] SaferWorldbyDesign, 'Chemical similarity search on RDT studies from REACH database / SaferWorldbyDesign', Observable. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting -
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

<https://observablehq.com/@saferworldbydesign/repeated-dose-toxicity-studies-from-reach-database>

- [46] EwC, 'EdelweissData™ CLP'. 2025. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://kit.edelweissconnect.com/dataexplorer?dataset=c4b8b8c4-527d-434b-92a4-c1a0eb60652f%3A1>
- [47] EwC, 'EdelweissData™ REACH Ecotox DB'. 2025. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://kit.edelweissconnect.com/dataexplorer?dataset=489143eb-a73a-493a-b75b-5d9a21905db1%3A1&q=%7B%7D>
- [48] 'NamastoxWeb'. Accessed: May 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://namastox.risk-hunt3r.net/>

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).

Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

**Innovate
UK**

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting -
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Appendices

Appendix A: Proposal for Physical-Chemical Data Collection

The proposed physical-chemical data to be collected as part of the assessment process. The data aims to support substance characterization and further analysis.

Property Name	Data can be provided? (Yes/No)									
	UoB	INVENT	CNR	LIST	TALOS	CID	VTT	NIBIO	SP	NORDTREAT
Chemical Composition										
Common Name										
Molecular Formula										
Monomer distribution										
Linkage distribution										
Branching coefficient										
Functional groups										
Molecular weight										
Number average molecular weight										
Molecular weight distribution										
Polydispersity index										
Degree of polymerization										
Decomposition temperature										
Glass transition temperature										
Melting point										
Water content										
Metals/elements content										
Physical state										
Color										
Odour										
Form										
Relative Density										
Bulk Density										
Viscosity										
pH										
Freezing point										
Boiling point/range										
Flash point										
Flammability										
Explosivity										
Autoflammability/Self-ignition temperature										
Vapour pressure										
physicochemical stability										
Molar Mass										
Molar mass repeating unit										
Oxidizing potential										
Acid dissociation constant (pKA)										
Water solubility										
Solubility in organic solvents										
Solubility in mg/100g standard fat										
Partition Coefficient (LogP)										

Figure 8. Screenshot of the proposal for physical-chemical data to be collected.

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

Innovate UK

This work was supported by UKRI Horizon Europe Underwriting - Innovate UK Council [1005409].